

RI-VIS - Third outreach and partnering event

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Executive Summary

In 2021, RI-VIS organised three international symposia focussing on research infrastructures (RI), with partner initiatives from Africa, Latin America and Australia. The Australia-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures was the third edition of this series and was held as a virtual event on October 5-7, 2021.

Delegates from Australia and European research infrastructures (RIs), science policy organisations and research institutions joined this symposium to learn about the RI landscapes and funding schemes in Australia and Europe, synergies between Australia and Europe RI, the importance of RIs in the life sciences and their contribution in addressing environment challenges and the climate change, as well as case studies of global RI initiatives.

Due to the current Covid-19 situation and pandemic-related travel restrictions, the symposium was organised as a virtual event. Despite the lack of opportunities for in person discussions, the organisers structured the symposium in such a way that the symposium participants had ample opportunities to exchange ideas, to network and discuss potentially new collaborations. Various formats – keynote lectures, panel discussions, virtual networking, virtual exhibitions - were chosen to facilitate the interaction between the speakers and participants.

Representatives from European RIs across scientific disciplines joined efforts to collaborate more efficiently and to raise awareness among the scientific user community, global RIs and science policy organisations, as part of the Horizon 2020-funded RI-VIS project (<https://ri-vis.eu>).

Detailed report on the deliverable

Background/Introduction

In Australia, the RI landscape is very well organised and structured. The Australian government's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS) [1] supports the excellence of the Australian research community through a network of world-class research infrastructures. Its policy for national RIs is consolidated periodically (every 5 years) and formulated in national roadmaps based on the feedback from the research community. The consultation process for the 2021 Roadmap, which will inform the investment plans for 2022 and 2024 is ongoing [2]. In Europe, European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) will publish its 2021 European Roadmap for RIs later this year [3]. As the publication of both roadmaps in Australia and Europe is imminent, the Australia-Europe symposium on RIs was very timely.

Many of the RIs, which have been included in the 2016 Australian RI Roadmap [4] and the 2018 ESFRI Roadmap [5], were involved in the organisation of this symposium (either as partner of the RI-VIS project and/or as a member of the International Organisation Committee, see below) and representatives of these RI actively participated in the symposium as speakers, session chairs and panellists.

Both regions have gained extensive experience with developing periodic RI roadmaps. Their RI landscapes share a lot of similarities in terms of ambition, organisation, and strategy (RISCAPE Report) [1]. RIs from both regions collaborate in several global RI initiatives. These aspects were key to the fruitful discussions during the three days of the symposium.

Description of work

The 'Australia-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures' was the third event in a series of three international symposia, which were organised as part of the RI-VIS project.

Organizing committee

Unlike the first two symposia, which focussed on Africa and Latin America, a larger local organizing committee was constituted with representatives from various Australian RI, which was chaired by Dr Carina Kemp of Australia's Academic and Research Network (AARNet). The organizing committee held regular virtual meetings and used text documents which were shared and edited online, in order to define the symposium agenda, session formats and list of invited speakers and panellists in a consultative process. The members of the International Organizing Committee, with an equal balance between female (8) and male (9) committee members, were:

Australian members of the International Organizing Committee:

- Carina Kemp (Australia's Academic and Research Network)
- Frankie Stevens (Australia's Academic and Research Network)
- Susie Robinson (Australian Plant Phenomics Facility)
- Wojtek Gosinski (National Imaging Facility)
- Stuart Newman (Therapeutic Innovation Australia)
- Luc Betbeder-Matibet (University of New South Wales)
- Julie Rothacker (Monash University)
- Michael Dobbie (Phenomics Australia)
- Merran Smith (Population Health Research Network)
- Tim Rawlings (Auscope)
- Michelle Heupel (Integrated Marine Observing System)
- Jo Curkpatrick (Australian Plant Phenomics Facility)

European members of the International Organizing Committee:

- Bahne Stechmann (EU-OPENSREEN)
- Viridiana Beltran Venegas (BBMRI-ERIC)
- Natalie Haley (Instruct-ERIC)
- Claudia Alén Amaro (Instruct-ERIC)

The virtual three-day symposium aimed to present different research infrastructure (RI) initiatives in Australia and Europe and to explore opportunities for collaborations between RIs from both world regions.

The symposium as an online conference

Due to the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, Australia's borders were closed at the time of the symposium and overseas travel and entry to Australia, especially for non-Australian citizens and permanent

residents, was strictly limited to help prevent the spread of COVID-19. Therefore, the organizing committee decided in early 2021 to hold a virtual symposium. Unfortunately, due to the virtual format and the stay-at-home lockdown in Melbourne and Victoria state, the main symposium could not be combined with satellite events, for example site visits of local RIs, universities and research institutes, or in-person poster sessions. However, the virtual format also had important advantages in comparison with in-person events: Unlike national or European meetings, where the time and effort to travel to the meeting is significantly lower for the majority of speakers and participants, the three RI-VIS symposia, which brought together speakers and attendees from two world-regions, would have required approximately one out of two speakers and participants to make intercontinental, long-haul flights if organised as an in person meeting. Considering that travelling to and from Australia in pre-Covid-19 times takes roughly three days, the virtual format lowers the barrier considerably for speaker and attendees from overseas to participate in this virtual symposium. This was also arguably helpful in engaging with high-level speakers, who may otherwise not be able to accept our invitations if their participation entails 2-3 days of overseas travelling. Furthermore, due to the lack of travelling, the carbon footprint of the symposium has been substantially reduced in comparison with the in-person format: Considering only the 109 European participants, the flights from Frankfurt to Sydney and back via Singapore would have produced 590 tonnes of CO2 emissions (source: myclimate.org).

The symposium website

A sub-section of the RI-VIS website was dedicated to the Australia-Europe symposium and informed interested colleagues about the symposium [7]. The website provided all relevant information, including an introduction to the symposium, a description and link to the White Paper "Recommendations towards cooperation between Australian and European research infrastructures", list of speakers and panellists with their photos and affiliations, the organising committee, registration link and agenda.

Promotion video

In order to promote the symposium, a short video was produced, as we did for the Latin America-Europe symposium. The video was shared via Twitter and other social media channels. The video is available on YouTube: [Australia - Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures](#). [8]

White paper with a focus on Australian-European RI collaborations

Prior to the symposium, the RI-VIS project published the White Paper entitled '*Recommendations towards cooperation between Australian and European research infrastructures*' [9]. RI-VIS (WP2) consulted experts from different scientific domains and on all career levels from both Europe and Australia with experience in RI collaborations. The White Paper collates the insights of experts from Australian RIs, European RIs, and policymakers, highlighting examples of Australian-European RI collaboration, best practices for successful collaboration, perceived challenges and bottlenecks, and from these presents a series of actionable recommendations. The White paper was made available to the symposium attendees in advance via the online symposium platform.

One of the recommendations of the white paper emphasised that 'Connecting on a personal level with others from abroad can lead to successful joint projects down the line'. By organising the Australia-Europe RI Symposium, RI-VIS aimed to initiate and strengthen such personal connections and to directly address this recommendation. The organisers of this symposium also strived to follow the recommendation that 'Overseas events should be customized to the host country's needs' by ensuring a geographical balance in the participation of speakers, panelists and attendees from both regions, and by proposing session topics that are relevant to RIs in Australia and Europe.

Online platform

Despite the advantages of virtual meetings in comparison with in person-meetings, the interaction, discussions and networking between the participants represents a challenge at virtual meetings, which requires special consideration. Virtual meetings can hardly replicate the networking and personal interactions, which usually take place during coffee breaks or social dinners at in person meetings. Also, site visits to local RIs, universities and research institutes cannot be organized, which would otherwise provide valuable insights. In response to these limitations, the duration of four hours per symposium day have been limited and the number of speaking slots was reduced as compared to

full-day meetings. Poster sessions have been integrated as a suitable alternative for individual (also early-career) scientists and potential RI users to present their work.

Prior to the Africa-Europe and Latin America-Europe symposia, the organizers looked at various commercial solutions for online platforms and tools to support the virtual symposia. A particular focus was that the platform should facilitate and encourage the active participation of the participants and the interaction and discussions among attendees throughout the symposium. Based on the positive experience with the online platform and tools, which the organisers tried and tested during the first two RI-VIS symposia, it was decided to work with the identical instruments, which were deployed during the Africa-Europa and Latin America-Europe symposia on RIs.

Besides the website, a commercial platform (<https://whova.com/>) was used to set-up a bespoke interactive online environment for the symposium compensating limitations of online events regarding direct exchange. It was available before, during and after the event. The platform offered various features to the symposium participants and speakers to engage with other attendees: participants had the opportunity to share with other attendees information about their name, affiliation, job titles and additional professional data via their 'attendee profiles'. In-app messaging allowed the attendees to reach out to other attendees and start a bilateral conversation. If the attendees wished to discuss specific topics with a larger audience, they could initiate a discussion in the 'community' area by adding a topic or social group. In addition to exchanging written messages, attendees were encouraged to invite other attendees to meet-ups and 'virtual meets' and discuss in groups through videoconferencing. Questions and suggestions to the organisers could be submitted by all attendees. In the 'handout' area, attendees could make handouts, flyers, brochures and other documents available to other colleagues. The participants were also invited to post comments and pictures: in total 67 photos have been shared by attendees.

Below the landing page of the event:

Whova Guides Organizing your own event?

Australia-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures
Oct 5 - 7, 2021 | Displaying in your local time: 2:53 PM | Switch to event time

Home
Agenda
Attendees
Community
Messages
Photos
Exhibitors
Leaderboard
Resources

Australia-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures

Exploring collaborations between Australia and Europe

5-7 October 2021

Virtual partnering event

ri-vis.eu @RI-VIS.eu RI-VIS

International cooperation in science and technology is an important part of addressing major global issues like climate change, infectious disease, food security, and natural disasters. Research Infrastructures are organizations providing state-of-the-art resources, services and expertise to scientists. The RI-VIS project unites research infrastructures across scientific domains to work together more efficiently and effectively and increase their visibility in society.

Research Infrastructures provide such coordination by offering access to key facilities, resources and expertise to empower research driven by scientific excellence and beyond the individual research capacity of different countries, economic sectors, or institutions.

We also invite representatives from funding agencies as well as policymakers to join and discuss opportunities for working together. By bringing together the right people we hope to create collaborations and initiate networks sustainably so that all stakeholders benefit.

Ahead of the symposium, the RI-VIS project has published the White Paper entitled "Recommendations towards cooperation between Australian and European research infrastructures". This White Paper collates the insights of experts from Australian RIs, European RIs, and policymakers, highlighting examples of Australian-European RI collaboration, best practices for successful collaboration, perceived challenges and bottlenecks, and from these presents a series of actionable recommendations.

We are looking forward to e-meeting you soon.

Australia-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures organisers

An important feature of the online platform, by which individual RIs could be showcased, was the 'virtual exhibition'. In total, 19 virtual exhibitions presented individual RIs, global RIs (Global-

Biolmaging), upcoming RI conferences (e.g. ICRI 2022), multi-RI clusters (e.g. European Life Sciences RIs) and training opportunities for RI managers (e.g. Executive Masters in Management of RIs or EMMRI). These initiatives, going far beyond the RI-VIS partnership, shared videos, handouts, marketing content, and photos. Live showcases could be organised to inform the symposium participants about the exhibiting RIs, their access models, service offers and other relevant aspects. The exhibitors also had the opportunity to engage with other attendees directly through the chat function of the online platform. Attendees, who contacted one of the exhibitors or requested additional information, automatically received the information of the exhibitions.

Networking session

An important aim of these meetings was to provide attendees with opportunities to reach out to colleagues and network. Unfortunately, this is arguably the most difficult part to replicate in a virtual format. After the positive feedback from the attendees of the first two RI-VIS meetings on the online networking tools available, the organisers agreed to employ <https://www.wonder.me/> again. All participants were invited to join the online networking area in the hour preceding the final day of the event. Attendees could be identified by their avatars, which could move around, deciding freely who they wished to talk to. As several attendees meet, a virtual videoconferencing bubble automatically opens so that the group can directly start a conversation. In addition to these smaller spontaneous networking groups, the organisers set-up virtual 'areas' around different themes to initiate discussions among like-minded attendees, who share an interest in a common topic. The bubbles can also be locked if participants wish to discuss undisturbed by other attendees, for example, about confidential project ideas. Messages and invitations to join a specific conversation could be sent to other attendees. In order to help attendees to locate a specific person, a list of participants that joined the networking session was available.

Due to the significant time difference between Australia and Europe, there was no ideal time for a joint networking session, which aimed to attract both Australian and European participants equally. Considering that the presentations and panel discussions provided food for further follow-up discussions, the organisers decided to schedule the networking sessions before the main programme at 07:00 CEST or 16:00 PM AEDT. The number joining the networking sessions was similar to that experienced during the first two events with approximately 20 participants but realistically

engagement in the networking session may have been reduced by the challenge of working across diverse time zones, even though the platform usefully provided the daily programme in each different time zone.

Agenda

Some experts, who were interviewed for the White paper, highlighted that one of the challenges for Australia-Europe collaborations is the extreme time difference between the two regions. At the time of the symposium, Sydney was 11 hours ahead of the UK, which makes longer online meetings, workshops and networking activities hard to manage. Therefore, the organisers of this symposium opted to limit the time of the main programme to four hours, between 8-12 am CEST or 5-9 pm AEDT. Though these times are not perfect and go beyond the usual working hours of most Australian attendees, the organisers agreed that these times represented the best compromise to accommodate participants, speakers and panellists from Australia to Europe.

The speakers and panelists came from Australia and seven European countries (AT, CZ, DE, ES, FI, NL, UK) and are affiliated to RIs as well as governmental and funding organisations. There was an equal balance between Australian (11) and European (10) speakers, and seven speakers were female.

Keynote addresses

At the Australia-Europe symposium, we changed the format of the event compared to the first two symposia. One of the main changes was the introduction of keynote speakers. Each of the three days of the symposium was kicked-off by inspirational addresses by keynote speakers. Dr. Cathy Foley, who was the keynote speaker on day one, has been the Chief Scientist of Australia since January 2021, and worked for many years at Australia's national science agency (CSIRO) in different roles, including Chief Scientist in 2018-2021. The keynote speaker on day 2 was Prof. Steve Brown, who is the former Chair of the International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium (IMPC), an international initiative to elucidate the function of every gene in the mouse genome, and Director of the MRC Harwell, a leading international centre for mouse phenotyping. Carolyn Shrives, the keynote speaker on day 3 is the Branch Manager - Research Policy and Programs at the Australian Government Department of Education and Training. She is also the Australian Delegate to the Group of Senior Officials (GSO) on global research infrastructures. The keynote speakers were also invited to join the panel discussion together with the speakers of the other sessions of the day.

Thematic sessions and speakers

The three symposium days addressed different topics: 'Research Infrastructure Landscapes in Australia and Europe' and 'Creating Synergies towards EU-AU collaborations' on day 1; 'Health/Cancer' with a session on 'The importance of Life Sciences Collaborations' on day 2; and 'Environment challenges/Climate Change' with a panel discussion on 'Tackling climate change and environmental challenges' on day 3. A session on 'Global Research Infrastructures' complemented day 3.

The organisers thanked all speakers of the sessions for their contributions and stimulating presentations:

After the opening words of the organisers, Dr Cathy Foley, Chief Scientist of Australia, gave the welcome address, which was chaired by Stuart Newman, CEO Therapeutic Innovation Australia (TIA). Dr Foley talked about the importance of RIs in delivering research with impact and talked about her experiences with research infrastructures and global collaborations. She also raised important questions, for example, how RIs will include machine learning and AI approaches, and the role of RIs in open research.

After the welcome session, Emeritus Professor Ian Smith, Vice-Provost (Research & Research Infrastructure) at Monash University moderated the panel discussion on 'Research Infrastructure landscapes'. Smith is responsible for the oversight and management of the university's research alliances and RIs, as well as developing and implementing strategies to meet future university RI needs in these areas. The panellists were Dr Bernadette Kelly, Senior Adviser at Department of the Prime Minister and Cabinet, Australia; Dr Inmaculada Figueroa, Vice-Chair of the European Strategic Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI), and Deputy Vice Director General for Internationalization of Science & Innovation in the Spanish Ministry of Science & Innovation, Spain; and Dr Dominik Sobczak, Deputy Head of Unit, Unit A3 ("R&I Actors and Research Careers"), Directorate General Research and Innovation, European Commission, Brussel, Belgium; Research policy officer on Research Infrastructures, and Executive Secretary of the European Strategic Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI). The panellists discussed the research infrastructure roadmaps in Australia and Europe, which will be updated in in 2021/22, and how the RI landscape is evolving both in Australia and in Europe. The panel discussion of day 1 was recorded (with the consent of all panellists) and the recording is available on the RI-VIS YouTube channel: [Panel Discussion | Australia - Europe Symposium Day 1](#):

After the panel discussion, Dr Claudia Alén Amaro, Senior Programme Manager Instruct-ERIC, chaired the session on 'Creating Synergies towards EU-AU collaborations'. This session presented concrete examples and initiatives of RI collaborations between Australia and Europe, featuring presentations by Dr Antje Keppler, Coordinator Global-BioImaging and Director Bio-Hub of Euro-BioImaging ERIC, Germany ([Video](#)); Dr Simon Musgrave, Senior Project Officer Language Data Commons of Australia (LDaCA), and Monash University, Australia ([Video](#)); and Dr Roland Pieruschka, Project Manager EMPHASIS, and Project Manager European Plant Phenotyping Network 2020 (EPPN2020), Germany ([Video](#)). The videos of all three talks are also available on the RI-VIS YouTube channel (see links above).

The second day revolved around the theme 'Health/cancer'. The 'Mission Cancer' is one of the missions in Horizon Europe [10] and an element of Europe's Beating Cancer Plan [11], and RIs make a critical contribution in this area. Prof. Steve Brown, Past Chair of the International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium (IMPC) and Director at the MRC Harwell, UK, set the scene of this day by giving the keynote lecture. The IMPC is a global effort with partners in Australia (Australian Phenomics Network) and Europe (MRC Harwell, Wellcome Sanger Institute, EMBL-EBI, Helmholtz-Zentrum München, the French national Infrastructure for mouse phenogenomics 'PHENOMIN', CNR Monterotondo, IMG Czech Centre for Phenogenomics and Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona), and is celebrating 10 years of research and mouse knockout production. Prof. Steve Brown highlighted in his presentation the importance of people and their connections to bring the global research community together. His presentation is also available online: [Steve Brown | Australia - Europe Symposium Day 2](#). This session was chaired by Michael Dobbie, CEO Phenomics Australia.

The following panel discussion on ‘The importance of Life Sciences Collaborations’ was chaired by Dr Stella Clark, Executive Director of Stella Connect P/L, and featured presentations by Sir Dave Stuart, Director Instruct-ERIC and Director Diamond, University of Oxford, UK; a joint presentation by Dr Andrew Lonie, Director of the Australian BioCommons, Australia and Dr Niklas Blomberg, Director of ELIXIR, UK; Stuart Newman, CEO Therapeutic Innovation Australia (TIA); Dr Michaela Mayrhofer, Head of ELSI Services and Research, BBMRI-ERIC, Austria; and Dr Steven McEachern, Director and Manager of the Australian Data Archive at the Australian National University, Australia. The audience learned about many great initiatives in the life-sciences community. The importance that individual scientists play within RIs was stressed by the panelists. The panel agreed that it is the interdisciplinary nature, which makes the RIs unique, and that the people and relationships across the RIs are key. The complete recording of this session is available online: [Panel Discussion | Australia - Europe Symposium Day 2](#)

SARS-CoV-2 at Diamond Light Source, UK

Summary: many key antiviral targets identified and resolved

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Ondřej Hradil, Masaryk University, Czech Republic, concluded the second day by announcing the upcoming ‘International Conference on Research Infrastructures (ICRI 2022), which will be held on Oct 19-21, 2022, in Brno, CZ. The ICRI 2022 conference will be an ideal platform to continue the discussions of this Australia-Europe symposium.

The third day focusses on another set of challenges, which constitutes an existential threat to Europe, Australia and the world: Climate change and environmental degradation. In Europe, the European Commission set-up the European Green Deal to overcome these challenges, which is funded with 600 billion Euro from the NextGenerationEU Recovery Plan and the EU’s seven-year budget. RIs are an important instrument and play an important role in addressing these challenges.

The keynote session on day 3 was a fireside chat format with Dr Carolyn Shives, Branch Manager - Research Policy and Programs of the Australian Government Department of Education and Training, in discussion with Dr Merran Smith, Chief Executive of Population Health Research Network (PHRN). The branch provides policy advice and oversight of the higher education research system, ranging from the provision of support for Higher Degree by Research in Australia’s universities, research policy, national research infrastructure including the 2016 National Research Infrastructure Roadmap and subsequent Investment Plan, and also manages the Australia’s National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS) program. Dr Shives is also the Australian Delegate to the Group of Senior Officials (GSO) on global research infrastructures, and the Assistant Secretary responsible for the development University Research Commercialisation Scheme in the Australian Government Department of Education, Skills and Employment. An important aspect of her keynote presentation focussed on strategies for the commercialisation of research by funding translational research and

supporting partnerships between universities and businesses. Dr Carolyn Shrides and Dr Merran Smith agreed that one of the challenges of RIs is to increase the visibility, and initiatives such as RI-VIS are very important for RIs to address issue. They also noted that international collaborations are reassuringly still very healthy despite the Covid-19 pandemic. The recording of this session is available on YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pSlSjBFQYew&t=37s>

The subsequent panel discussion, which was chaired by Dr Roland Pieruschka, Project Manager EMPHASIS, Jülich, Germany, explored how RIs contribute to ‘Tackling climate change and environmental challenges’. The panlists included delegates from Australian and European RIs: Dr Tim Rawling, CEO AuScope, Australia; Dr Werner Leo Kutsch, Director General Integrated Carbon Observation System (ICOS), Finland; and Dr Michelle Heupel, Director Australia’s Integrated Marine Observing System (IMOS), Australia. The panel discussed common challenges, like establishing global datasets, but also how to incentivise researchers to share their data. The panelists agreed that RIs in the environmental sciences have a exciting future of connected and automated sensors around the globe. The presentations showed how well the global community collaborates. The recording of the panel discussion can be found on YouTube: [Panel Discussion | Australia - Europe Symposium Day 3](#)

The final session of the symposium highlighted several examples of ‘Global Research Infrastructures’ and was chaired by Dr Natalie Haley, RI-VIS Project Manager Instruct-ERIC, Oxford, UK. In addition to the Global-BioImaging initiative and the International Mouse Phenotypic Consortium (IMPC), which were presented on day 1, Dr Donald Hobern, Data Director of Australian Plant Phenomics Facility (APPF), Australia; Dr Francisco Colomer, Director Joint Institute for VLBI ERIC (JIVE), The Netherlands; and Dr Alex de Marco, Associate Professor Monash University, Australia underlined in their presentations the importance of international collaborations for their research. Dr Francisco Colomer showed the audience that astronomy captures our imagination and the imagination of the general public, but also significantly contributes to the UN sustainability development goals. Furthermore, he illustrated that the VLBI researchers need to collaborate globally in order to make the impact that they need to achieve.

During their closing remarks, Dr Carina Kemp, Australian Chair of the Organizing Committee, and Dr Susan Daenke, Coordinator of the RI-VIS project, summarized the discussions of the three days of the symposium.

Attendee registration

The participation in this event was free, but registration was mandatory. The registration opened on August 16th, 2021. It was an explicit aim to attract equal numbers of participants from Australia and Europe. There was a total of 212 registrations, with an equal balance between Australian and European participants, as shown in the pie chart below. The registered participants represented delegates from RIs, governmental and funding organisations as well as independent researchers with an interest in this symposium.

Region	Total of registrations	%
Europe	109	51,41%
Australia	93	43,86%
Other	10	4,71%

The engagement of the attendees was high, as demonstrated by the following statistics:

In comparison with the first two RI-VIS outreach and partnering events, which focussed on Africa-Europe and Latin America-Europe RI collaborations, respectively, and taking into account the number of registrations for each event, the engagement of the attendees was higher at the Australia-Europe symposium than at the Latin America-Europe symposium. This observation may reflect the fact that there already exists a sound collaboration between the RI landscapes on both continents.

Engagement with the symposium via social media was also strong. Twitter analytics from the @RI_VIS_eu Twitter account show that over the three days of the event, @RI_VIS_eu tweets received over 30,100 impressions each day with an average engagement rate of 1.9%.

The recordings are available on the RI-VIS YouTube channel in the playlist [Australia—Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures](#), with a total of 88 video views, 40% of these views took place on the Whova Platform, which is available until January 2022. The most viewed video is the Panel Session on Day 2.

Note: The picture was shared on Twitter (with the consent of the attendees).

Satellite workshop

In conjunction with the main symposium, the European Infrastructure for Multi-scale Plant Phenomics (EMPHASIS) and the Australian Plant Phenomics Facility (APPF) organized a thematic satellite event. The workshop addressed invited participants with 22 in attendees from the Northern and Southern hemispheres. The goal of this workshop was to identify common existing and future areas of interests for the plant phenotyping communities in Australia and Europe. The key areas of interest addressed:

- from data acquisition to data management
- development, use and sharing of image analysis tools
- novel technology development
- training
- funding opportunities

The cooperation between Australia and Europe in plant phenotyping has a long history of existing cooperative activities at an institutional level, which will be now extended within a framework of a

Memorandum of Understanding between APPF and EMPHASIS linking the respective research infrastructure and communities from Australia and Europe. The MoU will be signed in early 2022.

Post-symposium survey

After the symposium, all attendees were asked to complete a short survey to monitor the quality of the symposium and satisfaction of the participants. Though the number of survey responses was limited (10), the respondents unanimously confirmed that the sessions meet the attendees' expectations, and all responded agreed that they would recommend the symposium to others. The respondents also had opportunities to share their key take-home messages from the symposium; e.g., that *there are good opportunities for further Australia-Europe engagement in RIs; the importance of RIs and international partnerships; and that international collaboration is crucial in particular to address emerging crisis*. Importantly, all respondents are interested in a follow-up symposium in the future.

Conclusion/Next steps

The Australian-Europe symposium was the third and last symposium, which has been organised by RI-VIS. This symposium was a very fruitful and successful event, as demonstrated by the impressive list of speakers and panellists, number of registrations, as well as stimulating discussions. The post-symposium feedback from participants, panellists, speakers and project partners was overall very positive, in particular with regards to the outcomes of the symposium, the online symposium platform and the content of the sessions throughout the three days. Importantly, the symposium attracted a similarly high number of registrations from both regions.

As expected, the time difference of up to 11 hours between Europe and Australia was a challenge. In order to accommodate convenient hours for European and Australian attendees, the duration of the symposium was limited to four hours per day, at between 08:00-12:00 CEST or 17:00-21:00 AEDT.

The virtual format of the event had benefits (e.g., no need to travel, CO2 emissions significantly reduced) and disadvantages (e.g., no local site visits, compromised opportunities to network). Notwithstanding these considerations, travelling to Australia for an in person meeting was strictly banned at the time of the symposium. The online symposium therefore aimed to replicate the experience of in-person meetings as best as possible, and several tried-and-tested online tools were employed to facilitate the active engagement and discussions among the symposium participants. The various formats included oral presentations, panel discussions, thematic workshops, and networking sessions. The conference organisers and panel discussion moderators encouraged the audience to actively contribute to the discussions and use the platform to reach out to other participants throughout the symposium.

The sessions were recorded, taking into account the speakers' consent, and uploaded to the RI-VIS YouTube channel and to the Whova platform.

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Appendices

Australia- Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures

#AustraliaEURResearchInfra

Virtual partnering event

5 October 2021

- 17:00 **Opening and Welcome of Participants**
 - [Carina Kemp](#) - Director of eResearch, AARNET, Australia
 - [Bahne Stechmann](#) - Head of Operations & Scientific Strategy, EU-OPENSREEN, Germany
 - [Susan Daenke](#) - Coordinator, Instruct-ERIC, UK
- 17:20 **Keynote Speech**
 - [Cathy Foley](#) - Chief Scientist of Australia
- 17:50 **Break**
- 18:15 **Panel Session: Research Infrastructure Landscapes**
 - [Bernadette Kelly](#) - Director National Research Infrastructure Policy, Australian Government Department of Education
 - [Inmaculada Figueroa](#) - Vice-Chair of the European Strategic Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI), and Deputy Vice Director General for Internationalization of Science & Innovation in the Spanish Ministry of Science & Innovation
 - [Dominik Sobczak](#) - Deputy Head of Unit, Unit A3 ("R&I Actors and Research Careers"), Directorate General Research and Innovation, European Commission, Brussel, Belgium; Research policy officer on Research Infrastructures, and Executive Secretary of the European Strategic Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI)
- 19:45 **Break**
- 20:00 **Creating Synergies Towards EU-AU Collaborations**
 - [Antje Keppler](#) - Coordinator Global-BiImaging and Director Bio-Hub of Euro-BiImaging ERIC, Germany
 - [Michael Haugh](#) - Language Data Commons of Australia
 - [Roland Pieruschka](#) - Project Manager EMPHASIS, and Project Manager European Plant Phenotyping Network 2020, Germany
- 21:00 **Wrap up of Day One**

6 October 2021

- 17:00 **Opening and Welcome of Participants**
- 17:15 **Keynote Speech**
 - [Michael Dobbie \(Chair\)](#) - CEO Phenomics Australia
 - [Steve Brown](#) - Former Director of the International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium (IMPC) and MRC Harwell, UK
- 17:55 **Break**
- 18:10 **Panel Session: The Importance of Life Sciences Collaborations**
 - [Sir Dave Stuart](#) - Director Instruct-ERIC, Director Diamond, University of Oxford, UK
 - [Andrew Lonie](#) - Director of the Australian BioCommons, Australia
 - [Niklas Blomberg](#) - Director of ELIXIR
 - [Stuart Newman](#) - CEO Therapeutic Innovation Australia (TIA)
 - [Michaela Mayrhofer](#) - Consortium of European Life Sciences RIs, Austria
 - [Steven McEachern](#) - Director and Manager of the Australian Data Archive at the Australian National University, Australia
- 21:00 **Announcement of ICRI 2022**
 - [Ondrej Hradil](#) - Masaryk University, Czech Republic
- 21:05 **Wrap up of Day Two**

*Times are given in UTC+11 = AEDT

7 October 2021

- 17:00 **Opening and Welcome of Participants**
 - [Susie Robinson](#) - Executive Director Australian Plant Phenomics Facility, and University of Adelaide
- 17:15 **Keynote Fireside Chat**
 - [Carolyn Shives](#) - Branch Manager - Research Policy and Programs, Australian Government Department of Education and Training, and Australian Delegate to the Group of Senior Officials (GSO) on global research infrastructures
- 17:55 **Break**
- 18:15 **Panel: Tackling climate change and environmental challenges**
 - [Tim Rawling](#) - CEO AuScope, Australia
 - [Werner Leo Kutsch](#) - Director General Integrated Carbon Observation System (ICOS), Finland
 - [Michelle Heupel](#) - Director Australia's Integrated Marine Observing System (IMOS), Australia
- 19:45 **Break**
- 20:00 **Global Research Infrastructures**
 - [Donald Hobern](#) - Data Director of Australian Plant Phenomics Facility (APPF), Australia
 - [Francisco Colomer](#) - Director Joint Institute for VLBI ERIC (JIVE), The Netherlands
 - [Alex De Marco](#) - Associate Professor Monash University, Australia
- 21:05 **Symposium Wrap Up**

AUSTRALIA-EUROPE SYMPOSIUM ON RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

OCTOBER 5 - 7, 2021

AUSTRALIA-EUROPE SYMPOSIUM ON RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

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whova app USAGE HIGHLIGHTS

OVERALL DOWNLOAD RATE

72% ATTENDEE DOWNLOAD RATE FOR WHOVA EVENTS
71%

SPEAKERS DOWNLOAD RATE

77% SPEAKERS DOWNLOADED
27 of 35

ATTENDEES LOVED OUR APP

86% TOOK THE SURVEY
6

PROFILE VIEWS IN APP

313

ATTENDEE NETWORKING

PRIVATE MESSAGES: 207
PHOTOS SHARED: 75

ANNOUNCEMENT OPEN RATE

62%

ANNOUNCEMENTS VIA IN-APP NOTIFICATIONS AND EMAILS
2

- ANNOUNCEMENTS
- Day 3: Australia - Europe Symposium ...
 - Thank you for attending the Australia ...

whova app COMMUNITY BOARD

DISCUSSION TOPICS POSTED

33

MOST POPULAR DISCUSSION TOPICS

- **Exhibitor Showcase**
19 messages
- **Session Q&A**
16 questions asked
- **Share Your Moments**
15 messages
- **Article Sharing**
15 articles shared
- **Shared links from Life Science Collaboration Session**
13 messages

COMMUNITY BOARD TOTAL MESSAGES

289

MEET-UP PARTICIPATION

6

MEET-UPS ORGANIZED

1

MOST POPULAR MEET-UPS

- **Tackling environmental challenges**
6 people joined this meet-up

whova app AGENDA HIGHLIGHTS

AGENDA IN-APP VIEWS

470

PERSONAL AGENDA SET-UP BY ATTENDEES

69

PERCENTAGE OF ATTENDEES SET
42%

AGENDA SESSIONS MOST POPULAR

SESSION POPULARITY BASED ON LIKES AND PERSONAL AGENDA ADDS

- Opening and welcome of participants
1 likes and 22 personal agenda adds
- Keynote Speaker
39 personal agenda adds
- Global Research Infrastructures
34 personal agenda adds
- Panel Session: Research Infrastructure Landscape
32 personal agenda adds
- Keynote Speaker - The importance of infrastructure in delivering research with impact; an overview of Australia
31 personal agenda adds

whova app MARKETING TOOLS YOU USED

AGENDA WEBPAGE VIEWS

1309

Your Agenda
Webpage Design

<https://whova.com/embedded/ev...>

REGISTRATION

192

whova app MOBILE & WEB APP ACTIVE USERS

TOTAL ACTIVE USERS

152

USERS WHO SIGNED IN EITHER MOBILE
OR WEB APP

USED BOTH MOBILE & WEB APP

38

USERS WHO DOWNLOADED THE MOBILE AND
SIGNED IN TO WEB APP

MOBILE APP ACTIVE USERS

36%

ATTENDEES WHO USED THE MOBILE
APP
55/152

WEB APP ACTIVE USERS

88%

ATTENDEES WHO USED THE WEB
APP
135/152

whova app
**COMMUNITY
HIGHLIGHTS**

DISCUSSION TOPICS POSTED

33

COMMUNITY BOARD TOTAL MESSAGES

289

ASK ORGANIZERS MESSAGES

13

BREAK-THE-ICE MESSAGES

37

OTHER CONFERENCES MESSAGES

11

ARTICLE SHARED MESSAGES

12

MOST FOLLOWED DISCUSSIONS

- Break the Ice!
9 people followed this topic
- Ask Organizers Anything
9 people followed this topic
- Any Other Conferences?
8 people followed this topic

PHOTOS SHARED

67

TOTAL LIKES FOR ALL PHOTOS

44

POPULAR PHOTOS MOST LIKED

MEET-UP PARTICIPATION

6

MEET-UPS ORGANIZED

1

MOST POPULAR MEET-UPS

- Tackling environmental challenges
6 people joined this meet-up

whova app ATTENDEE VIEWING ACTIVITY

ATTENDEES WATCHED TOTAL

112 TOTAL DURATION WATCHED
19 HRS

SESSIONS WITH VIDEO OR STREAM

24

WATCHED SESSIONS MOST POPULAR STREAMS

SESSION POPULARITY BASED ON NUMBER OF ATTENDEES

1. Opening and welcome of participants
5.0 hours, watched by 45 attendees
2. Panel Session: Research Infrastructure Landscape
1.4 hours, watched by 32 attendees
3. Welcome of participants
0.6 hours, watched by 31 attendees

WATCHED SESSIONS MOST POPULAR VIDEOS

SESSION POPULARITY BASED ON NUMBER OF ATTENDEES

1. Keynote Speaker - The importance of infrastructure in delivering research with impact; an overview of Australia
Watched by 1 attendees
2. Panel discussion
Watched by 1 attendees
3. Networking Session: Wonder at Australia-Europe Symposium
Watched by 1 attendees

whova app NETWORKING HIGHLIGHTS

PRIVATE MESSAGES 1-ON-1

207

ATTENDEE INTERACTION 1-ON-1

193

Attendees who have interacted with each other in private 1-on-1 messages

ATTENDEES INDICATED INTEREST

31

RECOMMENDED ATTENDEES

88

ATTENDEES MATCHED BASED OFF OF INTERESTS,
LOCATIONS, AFFILIATION

TOP RECOMMENDATION MATCHES

canberra, research infrastructures, international scientific cooperation, science leadership, melbourne, and more...

BIZ CARD SCANNED AND EXCHANGED

3

ATTENDEES PROFILE VIEWS

313

whova app ATTENDEE BREAKDOWN

ATTENDEE CATEGORIES

TOP 5 ATTENDEE CATEGORIES

	ATTENDEES
All attendees not in other categories	158
Speakers	34
Exhibitors	23
Organizers	5

ATTENDEE AFFILIATION

TOP 5 ATTENDEE AFFILIATION

	ATTENDEES
BBMRI-ERIC	5
Instruct-ERIC	5
Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC)	4
Phenomics Australia	4
EU-OPENSREEN ERIC	3

MOST ACTIVE ATTENDEES

TOP 5 MOST ACTIVE BY APP ACTION

	ACTIONS
Susie Robinson	379
Viridiana Beltran	366
Natalie Haley	361
Craig Humphrey	211
Richard Poiré	197

Whova

whova app AGENDA WEBPAGE

YOUR AGENDA WEBPAGE DESIGN

AGENDA WEBPAGE URL

<https://ri-vis.eu/>

WHOVA TEMPLATE USED

BALTIC

Event Schedule

📅 Displaying agenda in event timezone (1:39 AM AEDT)

Tuesday, October 5

<p>3:30 PM-5:00 PM Community Workshops: Plant phenotyping workshop - finding common ground and reaching common goals <small>Speakers: Susie Robinson, Roland Pieruschka, Belinda Cay</small></p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: center; margin-top: 10px;"> </div> <p style="font-size: 0.8em; margin-top: 5px;"> <small>The Australian Pla... Read More</small> </p>	<p>5:00 PM-5:20 PM Opening and welcome of participants <small>📺 Live Stream: Join stream</small> <small>Speakers: Carina Kemp, Susan Daenke, Viridiana Beltran</small></p>
<p>5:20 PM-5:50 PM Keynote Speaker - The importance of infrastructure in delivering research with impact; an overview of Australia <small>📺 Live Stream: Join stream</small> <small>Speakers: Stuart Newman, Dr Cathy Foley</small></p>	<p>5:50 PM-6:15 PM Break</p>
<p>6:15 PM-7:45 PM Panel Session: Research Infrastructure Landscape <small>📺 Live Stream: Join stream</small> <small>Speakers: Ian Smith, Inmaculada Figueroa, Dominik Sobczak, Bernadette Kelly</small> <small>4 Subsessions</small></p>	<p>7:45 PM-8:00 PM Break</p>
<p>8:00 PM-9:00 PM Creating Synergies towards EU-AU collaborations <small>📺 Live Stream: Join stream</small> <small>Speakers: Claudia Alen Amaro, Antje Keppler, Simon Musgrave, Roland Pieruschka</small> <small>3 Subsessions</small></p>	<p>9:00 PM-9:45 PM Wrap up of day 1 <small>📺 Live Stream: Join stream</small></p>

Wednesday, October 6

<p>5:00 PM-5:15 PM Welcome of participants <small>📺 Live Stream: Join stream</small></p>	<p>5:15 PM-5:55 PM Keynote Speaker <small>📺 Live Stream: Join stream</small> <small>Speakers: Michael Dobbie, Steve Brown</small></p>
<p>5:55 PM-6:10 PM Break</p>	<p>6:10 PM-9:00 PM Panel Session: The importance of Life Sciences Collaborations <small>📺 Live Stream: Join stream</small> <small>Speakers: Andrew Lonie, Niklas Blomberg, Stuart Newman, Michaela Th. Mayrhofer, Steven McEachern, Sir Dave Stuart, Stella Clark</small> <small>7 Subsessions</small></p>
<p>9:00 PM-9:05 PM Announcement of ICRl 2022 - International Conference on Research Infrastructures in Oct 19-21, 2022, Brno, CZ <small>📺 Live Stream: Join stream</small> <small>Speaker: Ondřej Hradil</small></p>	<p>9:05 PM-9:45 PM Wrap up of day 2 <small>📺 Live Stream: Join stream</small></p>

Thursday, October 7

<p>4:00 PM-5:10 PM Networking Session: Wonder at Australia-Europe Symposium <small>📺 Live Stream: Join stream</small> <small>Location: https://bit.ly/3Wmshet</small></p>	<p>5:10 PM-5:20 PM Break</p>
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We invite you to join the "Wonder At RI-VIS Symposium" session. This virtual networking session provides a platform and opportunity for attendees to talk and discuss the issues that matter to them.

TOTAL AGENDA WEBPAGE VIEWS

1309

agenda stats shown are not from the app

INDIVIDUAL AGENDA TOTAL VIEWS

679

agenda stats shown are not from the app

TOP 10 AGENDAS

1. **Global Research Infrastructures**
2. **Community Workshops: Plant phenotyping workshop - finding common ground and reaching common goals**
3. **Networking Session: Wonder at RI-VIS Symposium**
4. **Panel Session: Research Infrastructure Landscape**
5. **Opening and welcome of participants**
6. **Panel Discussion: Tackling climate change and environmental challenges**
7. **Panel Session: The importance of Life Sciences Collaborations**
8. **Francisco Colomer - Director Joint Institute for VLBI ERIC (JIVE), The Netherlands**
9. **Creating Synergies towards EU-AU collaborations**
10. **Welcome of participants**

whova app SPEAKER WEBPAGE

YOUR SPEAKER WEBPAGE DESIGN

SPEAKER WEBPAGE URL

https://whova.com/embedded/speakers/rivis_202109/

Speakers

Alex de Marco Associate Professor Monash University	Andrew Lonie Director Australian BioCommons	Antje Keppler Coordinator Global-Biologin... Euro-Biologin ERIC	Bahne Stechmann Head of Operations &... EU-OPENSREEN ERIC
B			
Bernadette Kelly Director, National Research... Australian Government...	Carina Kemp Digital Research Advisor Independent	Carolyn Shives Assistant Secretary -... Department of Education, Skills...	Claudia Alen Amaro Senior Programme... Instruct-ERIC
Dominik Sobczak Deputy Head of Unit European Commission,...	Donald Hobern Data Management Director Australian Plant Phenomics Facill...	Dr Cathy Foley Australia's Chief Scientist Office of Chief Scientist, Australia	Ian Smith Emeritus Professor Monash University
Indi Hodgson-Johnston Deputy Director Australia's Integrated Marin...	Inmaculada Figueroa Vice Deputy-Director General... Ministry of Science and Innovation,...	Margaret Leggett Assistant Secretary... Australian Government...	Merran Smith Chief Executive Population Health Research Netwo...
Michael Dobbie CEO Phenomics Australia	Michaela Th. Mayrhofer Head of ELSI Services and... BBMRI-ERIC	Michelle Heupel Director Australia's Integrated Marin...	Natalie Haley Project Manager Instruct-ERIC

whova app EXHIBITOR WEBPAGE

YOUR EXHIBITOR WEBPAGE DESIGN

EXHIBITOR WEBPAGE URL

https://whova.com/embedded/exhibitor/rivis_202109/

The screenshot displays a web interface for an exhibitor webpage. At the top right, there are icons for 'Print / Download' and social media links for Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn. Below this is a search bar with a dropdown menu set to 'All Exhibitors' and a search icon. The main content area is titled 'All Exhibitors' and features a grid of 24 exhibitor cards. Each card includes a logo, the exhibitor's name, a short description, and a URL. The exhibitors listed are: AMRI - European Alliance of Medical Research Infrastructures, Australian Plant Phenomics Facility (APPF), BBMRI-ERIC, ECRIN-ERIC, EMPHASIS, ENVRI, ESS ERIC, EU-OPENSREEN ERIC, Euro-Biolmaging, European Life Science Research Infrastructure (ELSI), Executive Masters in Management of Research Infrastructures (EMMI), Global Biolmaging, ICRI, and INFRAFRONTIER.

whova app EVENT WEBSITE

YOUR EVENT WEBSITE DESIGN

EVENT WEBSITE URL

https://whova.com/web/rivis_202109/

AUSTRALIA-EUROPE SYMPOSIUM ON RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

whova app REGISTRATION

TICKETS TOTAL SOLD

192

REGISTRATION PERIOD

Displaying the most recent 8 weeks of registration

*Week 0: total of all weeks prior

Whova

TICKET SUMMARY

TICKET	PRICE	ORDERS	REVENUE
General Admission	\$0.00	192/500	\$0.00
Total		192/500	\$0.00

YOUR REGISTRATION PAGE

REGISTRATION URL

https://whova.com/portal/registration/rivis_202109/

STEPS: 1/3

Attendee Registration

Select tickets and quantity

Ticket	Price	Quantity
General Admission	FREE	0

Sales end on October 20, 2021 at 06:00 AM

Next

whoa app EXHIBITOR REPORT

EXHIBITOR TOTAL

19

LEADS GENERATED TOTAL

5

ADDED VIDEOS TOTAL

14

ADDED LIVE SHOWCASES TOTAL

1

ADDED DOCUMENTS TOTAL

19

PHOTOS TOTAL TOTAL

16

EXHIBITOR PHOTOS MOST LIKED

EXHIBITOR LEAD GENERATION

4

ESS ERIC

1

**Australian Plant Phenomics
Facility**

EXHIBITOR BOOTH STATS

VISITS	LIKES	CHAT	STREAM	VIDEO	DOC VIEWS	PROMO CLAIMED
5	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

AMRI - European Alliance of Medical Re...

VISITS	LIKES	CHAT	STREAM	VIDEO	DOC VIEWS	PROMO CLAIMED
27	4	1	N/A	19	N/A	N/A

Australian Plant Phenomics Facility

VISITS	LIKES	CHAT	STREAM	VIDEO	DOC VIEWS	PROMO CLAIMED
24	4	0	N/A	18	N/A	N/A

BBMRI-ERIC

VISITS	LIKES	CHAT	STREAM	VIDEO	DOC VIEWS	PROMO CLAIMED
8	3	0	N/A	N/A	1	N/A

ECRIN-ERIC

VISITS	LIKES	CHAT	STREAM	VIDEO	DOC VIEWS	PROMO CLAIMED
18	1	1	N/A	11	2	N/A

EMPHASIS

VISITS	LIKES	CHAT	STREAM	VIDEO	DOC VIEWS	PROMO CLAIMED
41	4	2	N/A	11	1	N/A

ENVRI

VISITS	LIKES	CHAT	STREAM	VIDEO	DOC VIEWS	PROMO CLAIMED
27	2	0	N/A	13	N/A	4

ESS ERIC

VISITS	LIKES	CHAT	STREAM	VIDEO	DOC VIEWS	PROMO CLAIMED
7	4	0	N/A	3	N/A	N/A

EU-OPENSREEN ERIC

WhoVa

CREATED BY WHOVA INC.

SPONSORS, EXHIBITORS AND CAREER FAIR

	VISITS	LIKES	CHAT	STREAM	VIDEO	DOC VIEWS	PROMO CLAIMED
	9	1	0	N/A	8	N/A	N/A

Euro-BioImaging

	VISITS	LIKES	CHAT	STREAM	VIDEO	DOC VIEWS	PROMO CLAIMED
	6	2	0	N/A	5	N/A	N/A

European Life Science Research Infrastr...

	VISITS	LIKES	CHAT	STREAM	VIDEO	DOC VIEWS	PROMO CLAIMED
	6	1	1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Executive Masters in Management of R...

	VISITS	LIKES	CHAT	STREAM	VIDEO	DOC VIEWS	PROMO CLAIMED
	8	2	0	N/A	7	2	N/A

Global BioImaging

	VISITS	LIKES	CHAT	STREAM	VIDEO	DOC VIEWS	PROMO CLAIMED
	3	2	0	N/A	2	N/A	N/A

ICRI

	VISITS	LIKES	CHAT	STREAM	VIDEO	DOC VIEWS	PROMO CLAIMED
	9	2	0	N/A	N/A	2	N/A

INFRAFRONTIER

	VISITS	LIKES	CHAT	STREAM	VIDEO	DOC VIEWS	PROMO CLAIMED
	14	4	0	N/A	11	1	N/A

Instruct-ERIC

	VISITS	LIKES	CHAT	STREAM	VIDEO	DOC VIEWS	PROMO CLAIMED
	12	3	0	N/A	N/A	1	N/A

National Imaging Facility (NIF)

	VISITS	LIKES	CHAT	STREAM	VIDEO	DOC VIEWS	PROMO CLAIMED
	36	2	0	N/A	N/A	2	N/A

Phenomics Australia

AUSTRALIA-EUROPE SYMPOSIUM ON RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

WhoVa

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SPONSORS, EXHIBITORS AND CAREER FAIR

VISITS	LIKES	CHAT	STREAM	VIDEO	DOC VIEWS	PROMO CLAIMED
15	4	0	N/A	12	1	N/A

Population Health Research Network

VISITS	LIKES	CHAT	STREAM	VIDEO	DOC VIEWS	PROMO CLAIMED
40	2	0	N/A	27	3	N/A

Research Infrastructure Viewpoint Tech...

AUSTRALIA-EUROPE SYMPOSIUM ON RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

Appendix 2: Post-event survey results

Timestamp	Country of residence	Please comment on what you liked about the symposium and your recommendations on what could be improved?	Overall, did the sessions meet your expectations?	Which session did you like in particular?	How valuable were the networking opportunities?	Did the symposium structure give ample time to interact with other attendees?	Are you interested in a follow-up symposium in the future?	Would you recommend the symposium to others?	How well organized was the conference?	How would you rate the Whova app?	What are your key take-home messages from this symposium?
07/10/2021 10:18:00	Australia	I enjoyed the Whova platform which assisted with engaging with fellow attendees. Timing wasn't fantastic for someone with family commitments, though understand difficulties in arranging a symposium btw EU and Aus.	Yes	The first session on research infrastructure importance/landscape	Somewhat	Yes	Yes	Yes	Very	Very good	Importance of defining and communicating 'impact' for research infrastructure.
07/10/2021 13:44:00	Australia	I have really enjoyed the community spirit that has been developing through the conference platform and ability to participate on the go due to the app. I would like to see a clearer pathway to actions arising from presentations.	Yes	panel on environment and climate.	Very	Yes	Yes	Yes	Somewhat	Excellent	networking rules!
07/10/2021 17:41:00	Australia	Interesting presentations, and the discussion topics online were good. Would be nice for the timezones to be more equally recognised i.e. not always evening (non business hours) for the Australians :)	Yes	Day 1 presentation by Dominik Sobczak- interesting overview of EC policy, the EU landscape for RI etc.	Somewhat	Yes	Yes	Yes	Very	Excellent	We share many similar challenges around capturing impact, managing data, ensuring recognition of the role of our RIs by researchers.
08/10/2021 10:49:00	United Kingdom	I AM SORRY, I COULD NOT WATCH THE SYMPOSIUM - EVEN THOUGH I REGISTERED FOR IT. DO NOT KNOW WHY THINGS DID NOT CLICK. WILL BE HAPPY, IF I CAN SEE THE RECORDED VERSION.	No	NOT APPLICABLE	Not at all	No	Yes	Yes	Not at all	Poor	IT IS EVIDENT THAT EVEN IF WE CANNOT SEE, THERE IS NO BODY TO COMMUNICATE. SORRY!
08/10/2021 12:01:00	Australia	Liked both structure and content Excellent speakers Numerous senior attendees ie heads of infrastructures Good audience engagement, with session Chairs/speakers allowing time for questions. Manageable number of attendees which helped interaction Lively chat and plenty of breaks All sessions ran to time (well done all!) Wonder was good. Consider shortening any future events to three hours per day Last but not least, many thanks to the EU RIs for taking the initiative to set up the event :-)	Yes	The exemplars of global infrastructure collaboration eg GBI and IMPC	Very	Yes	Yes	Yes	Very	Very good	There are good opportunities for further EU-Australia engagement on research infrastructures
08/10/2021 16:32:00	finland	I was not able to attend each session but those I did attend were all running very smooth, I also enjoy the platform.	Yes	Tackling climate change and environmental challenges Global RIs	Somewhat	Yes	Yes	Yes	Very	Very good	We need some established mechanisms for the collaboration, knowledge transfer and information exchange between European RIs and their global counterparts
08/10/2021 18:03:00	France	Great speakers and nice opening on the possible collaborations between the two regions	Yes	The sessions I attended (keynotes, Ifesciences, closing) were all very good. Unfortunately the networking did not fall at times where I was available. Thanks to the organising committee. Great symposium	Somewhat	No	Yes	Yes	Extremely	Fair	I found the discussion on the importance of research infrastructures and international partnerships very interesting. The balance between the size of the infrastructure and the capacity to work at the scale in collaboration with countries such as australia - how to integrate or partner were very interesting and at times somewhat sector dependent.
08/10/2021 19:27:00	United Kingdom	I thought the symposium was well organised and the speakers were brilliant	Yes	I only participated in some of the sessions but very much liked hearing Cathy Foley presentation and Francisco Colomer but I also found Werner presentation very interesting	Somewhat	Yes	Yes	Yes	Extremely	Very good	Need to be more open with our communication involving other scientists to work together as a team instead of keep re-inventing the wheel
27/10/2021 03:14:00	UK	The organising committee with membership from both regions was very useful and something to keep. Communication with the Australian scientific community could have been better	Yes	The first session was particularly useful	Somewhat	Yes	Yes	Yes	Extremely	Very good	International collaboration is crucial in particular to address emerging crisis